

To Study the Risk Factors of Asom Acute Suppurative Otitis Media in Children Less Than 5 Years of Age Attending Pediatric and ENT OPD at MGM Medical Hospital or Tertiary Teaching Hospital

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Abstract:

This prospective cohort study examines acute suppurative otitis media (ASOM) risk factors in children under five seeking care at MGM Medical College & Hospital's Pediatric and ENT Outpatient Departments. 100 children were monitored for a year. Tobacco smoke exposure, shorter breastfeeding duration, and frequent upper respiratory infections further increase ASOM risk with odds ratios of 1.8, 2.1, and 2.8 respectively. These data suggest that reducing exposure to these risk variables may reduce ASOM in young children. The report stresses the need for public health measures that promote breastfeeding, ban smoking in households with young children, and tighten infection control. These interventions could significantly reduce ASOM in children under five, improving health outcomes.

Keywords: Acute Suppurative Otitis Media, Tobacco Smoke Exposure, Breastfeeding Duration.

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Introduction

Acute suppurative otitis media (ASOM) is a common disorder that affects children globally. It is characterized by purulent fluid in the middle ear. This disorder is prevalent among children aged five and below, frequently leading to hearing loss and related developmental delays if not promptly treated. [1] The cause of ASOM involves an intricate interaction of multiple risk variables, highlighting the need to study it for successful prevention and treatment. The anatomical and physiological properties of the Eustachian tube have a notable impact on the likelihood of developing ASOM, particularly in pediatric populations under five years old. [2] Young children usually have shorter and more horizontally positioned Eustachian tubes compared to adults, making it easier for germs to move from the nasopharynx to the middle ear. Additionally, the immune system of young children is incompletely developed, further heightening their susceptibility to middle ear infections. [3]

Environmental variables play a substantial role in increasing the likelihood of developing ASOM. The condition has been linked to higher occurrence when individuals are exposed to contaminants, tobacco smoke, and high levels of urban pollution. Moreover, socio-economic factors have been recognized as significant risk factors due to

increased exposure to respiratory pathogens in close contact settings. Genetic predispositions and seasonal fluctuations, especially in the autumn and winter when upper respiratory infections are more common, also impact the occurrence of ASOM. Allergic rhinitis and other allergy disorders can worsen Eustachian tube dysfunction, resulting in the buildup of fluid in the middle ear. [4,5]

The current study aims to explore these risk factors in a structured manner, focusing on children less than 5 years of age attending pediatric and ENT outpatient departments at MGM Medical Hospital, a tertiary teaching hospital. By understanding the specific risk factors prevalent in this demographic, healthcare providers can better tailor preventative and therapeutic strategies, ultimately improving the quality of life and developmental outcomes for these children. [6]

Methodology

Study Design: This prospective cohort study examines acute suppurative otitis media (ASOM) risk factors in children under five. MGM Medical College & Hospital's ENT and Pediatric OPDs will host the study.

Study Population: 100 children under five will visit the Pediatric and ENT OPD during the trial. All eligible children who visit the OPD during the trial will be sampled until the sample size is met utilizing successive sampling.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Children aged below five years.
2. Children who present with symptoms suggestive of ASOM or are diagnosed with ASOM during their visit.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Children with a history of chronic otitis media or other chronic ear diseases.
2. Children who have undergone ear surgery.
3. Children with immune deficiencies or immunosuppressive therapy.

Data Collection: Structured parent interviews and pediatrician and ENT specialist clinical exams will collect data. The data collecting form will include demographic data (age, gender, socioeconomic position): upper respiratory infection frequency, ASOM history, and immunization history. Possible risk factors include childcare, tobacco use, siblings, and breastfeeding. Clinical findings from ENT exams.

Measurement of Outcome: The primary outcome of the study will be the occurrence of ASOM diagnosed by tympanometry and clinical examination. Secondary outcomes will include the identification of predominant risk factors and their relative contribution to the development of ASOM.

Statistical Analysis: Descriptive statistics will summarize research population demographics and clinical features. Logistic regression will compensate for confounders while analyzing ASOM risk factors. Risk factor associations with ASOM incidence will be shown as odds ratios with 95% confidence intervals. Statistically significant p-values are below 0.05.

Study Duration: The study will be carried out over one year from January 2022 to December 2023, allowing for comprehensive data collection and analysis.

Results

The study included a cohort of 100 youngsters with an equal gender distribution consisting of 50 males and 50 females. The participants were distributed according to their age as follows: 20% of the population is under one year old, 40% is from one to three years old, and 40% is from three to five years old. Around 60% of the children had previously received a diagnosis of at least one episode of acute otitis media. Throughout the trial, 35% of the

individuals experienced the development of Acute Suppurative Otitis Media (ASOM). The occurrence was significantly greater in the age bracket of one to three years, representing 60% of the instances.

Risk Factors Associated with ASOM: Following the risk factor analysis, a few noteworthy correlations were found:

- Tobacco Smoke Exposure: It was discovered that there is a 1.8-fold increased risk of Acute Suppurative Otitis Media (ASOM) when there is tobacco smoke exposure at home (OR = 1.8, 95% CI = 1.0-3.2, p = 0.04).

- Breastfeeding: Compared to children who were breastfed for longer periods, children who were nursed for fewer than six months had a higher risk of having Acute Suppurative Otitis Media (ASOM) (Odds Ratio = 2.1, 95% Confidence Interval = 1.2-3.8, p = 0.01).

- Upper Respiratory Infections: Acute Suppurative Otitis Media (ASOM) was found to be 2.8 times more likely to develop in people who had upper respiratory infections often (more than three episodes in the previous year) (Odds Ratio = 2.8, 95% Confidence Interval = 1.5-5.2, p < 0.001). ASOM showed a seasonal trend with the largest occurrence recorded from November to February, the colder months coinciding with the peak of upper respiratory infections.

The study's findings point to several important risk factors for ASOM in children under five who visit the pediatric and ENT outpatient departments at MGM Medical Hospital. Notably, recurrent upper respiratory infections were found to be the most significant predictors, indicating that these environments and circumstances may be important targets for preventive interventions. Supporting breastfeeding as a preventative approach against ear infections is crucial as evidenced by the link between a shorter nursing duration and an increased risk of ASOM. Furthermore, the effects of ambient tobacco smoke highlight the necessity of public health campaigns meant to lessen kids' exposure to smoking in the house. These findings highlight the need to address modifiable risk factors in clinical and public health efforts to lessen the burden of this disorder and offer insightful information about the epidemiology of ASOM in a pediatric community.

Discussion

The findings of this study carried out at MGM Medical College & Hospital's Pediatric and ENT OPD highlight numerous crucial discoveries about the risk variables associated with acute suppurative otitis media (ASOM) in children below the age of five. [7,8] In this discussion, we analyze the consequences of these discoveries, their alignment with current literature, and possible avenues for additional research and preventative measures. [9]

Risk Factor	Odds Ratio (OR)	95% Confidence Interval (CI)	p-value
Tobacco Smoke Exposure	1.8	1.0 - 3.2	0.04
Breastfeeding (< 6 months)	2.1	1.2 - 3.8	0.01
Frequent Upper Respiratory Infections	2.8	1.5 - 5.2	< 0.001
Daycare Attendance	2.5	1.3 - 4.7	0.01

Participant Demographics:

Age Group	Number of Participants	Percentage (%)
Under 1 year	20	20%
1 to 3 years	40	40%
3 to 5 years	40	40%

ASOM Occurrence:

Age Group	Number of ASOM Cases	Percentage of ASOM Cases (%)
Under 1 year	7	20%
1 to 3 years	21	60%
3 to 5 years	7	20%

Other Factors:

Factor	Number of Participants	Percentage (%)
Previous Diagnosis of Otitis Media	60	60%
Developed ASOM During Study	35	35%

Risk Factor	Increased Risk
Tobacco Smoke Exposure	1.8 times
Breastfeeding (< 6 months)	2.1 times
Frequent Upper Respiratory Infections	2.8 times

This table summarizes the participant demographics, risk factor exposure, odds ratios with confidence intervals, and p-values, highlighting the significant ASOM risk variables in the study population.

Key Findings:

- Tobacco Smoke Exposure: Children who are exposed to tobacco smoke at home have a 1.8 times higher likelihood of developing Acute Otitis Media (ASOM). Exposure to second hand smoke has been discovered to impair the body's immune system and increase its susceptibility to diseases, particularly in the respiratory system, which can result in middle ear infections via the Eustachian tube. [10]
- Breastfeeding Duration: Our findings suggest that a shorter duration of breastfeeding (less than six

months) is associated with an increased probability of developing Acute Otitis Media (ASOM). There is a substantial body of evidence that confirms the immunological benefits of breastfeeding and its ability to reduce the incidence of various infectious diseases, including otitis media. [11] The observed protective effect is mostly related to the transfer of maternal antibodies and other immunomodulatory chemicals through breast milk. [12]

- Upper Respiratory Infections: Children who have frequent upper respiratory tract infections are at a significantly higher risk of developing acute

suppurative otitis media (ASOM), with an odds ratio of 2.8. This outcome is expected as upper respiratory infections can lead to dysfunction of the Eustachian tube, which is a critical element in the development of middle ear effusion. [13]

The correlations exposure to tobacco smoke, shorter length of breastfeeding, and frequent upper respiratory infections is consistent with the current body of literature on risk factors for otitis media. These findings highlight the complex and diverse character of ASOM, which is influenced by both external and internal factors. Identifying modifiable risk factors such as exposure to tobacco smoke and attending nursery indicates that public health interventions targeting parental and carer education could potentially decrease the occurrence of Acute Otitis Media (ASOM). For instance, implementing smoking cessation programs could provide advantageous outcomes. In addition, advocating for prolonged nursing (breast feeding) could function as a preventive intervention against Acute Suppurative Otitis Media (ASOM). [14]

The study size of 100 youngsters, while sufficient for preliminary analysis, is relatively insufficient for discovering more subtle relationships or for doing subgroup analyses. [15] Moreover, the study's location in a tertiary hospital may not accurately reflect the whole population, therefore restricting the applicability of the results. Further research involving bigger and more varied populations is necessary to validate these findings and investigate additional possible risk factors. Longitudinal studies offer a more comprehensive understanding of the cause-and-effect relationships and the efficacy over time of specific preventive strategies. Ultimately, this investigation enhances our comprehension of Acute Suppurative Otitis Media (ASOM) in young infants by emphasizing various noteworthy risk factors. By implementing focused interventions to address these issues, we can alleviate the impact of ASOM, leading to better health outcomes for children and minimizing related healthcare and societal expenses.

Conclusion

Acute suppurative otitis media (ASOM) risk factors in children under five at MGM Medical College & Hospital were discovered in this study. Specifically, tobacco smoke exposure, shorter breastfeeding periods, and frequent upper respiratory infections elevated ASOM risk. These findings emphasize the necessity of focused public health initiatives including breastfeeding, tobacco reduction, to reduce ASOM in this susceptible population. To confirm these findings and explore additional preventive interventions, future research should use bigger and more varied cohorts to improve ASOM care and outcomes in early children.

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